

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

PATHOGENIC FUNGI LIVING ON PLANTS CULTURALLY CULTIVATED IN AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

The understanding of the importance of processes occurring in the desired ecosystem, as well as the clarification of the role of individual components, begins with the identification of taxonomic groups of living organisms inhabiting that area. We present the results of a research of the pathogenic mycobiota of herbaceous plants cultivated in Azerbaijan. It is shown that 73 plant species are infested by 105 species of fungi. Among the identified fungi are such species as *Alternaria alternata*, *Ascochyta pisi*, *Botrytis cinerea*, *Fuzarium moniliforme*, *F. oxysporium*, *Penicillium cuclopium*, *Sclerotinia libertiana*, *Septoria lucopersici*, *Verticillium dahliae* etc., which are part of the dominant core of mycobiota of the investigated plants and cause of various diseases. The dynamics of some of them (*fusarium*, powdery mildew) is characterized by progression. As is known, the factors that limit the biological productivity of plants used for various purposes include diseases caused by fungi. These play an important role in the development of research in Azerbaijan, where different diseases are studied in plants.

Keywords: pathogenic fungi, Azerbaijan, herbaceous plants.

Material and Metod. The natural conditions of the Republic of Azerbaijan are extremely diverse and have long attracted the attention of researchers with their rich flora and fauna. Thus, almost all the relief elements are present in a relatively small area [4]. It is known that the flora of Azerbaijan includes about 4,500 species of plants, among which there are many species with medicinal, forage, and nutritional values [9]. In addition, flora is currently one of the main sources providing the world's population with vital materials, including agricultural products, which are cultivated in all territories in Azerbaijan [6]. One of the reasons preventing the cultivation of various crops is diseases caused by microorganisms, primarily fungi, due to which the annual loss of yield is at least 10% [3]. To prevent these losses, a detailed study of the pathogenic mycobiota of cultivated plants is necessary. So, without the necessary information, it is impossible, on the one hand, to scientifically substantiate the need for protective measures, on the other, to obtain breeding materials for the creation of resistant varieties.

Results. Currently, about 50 species of plants are culturally cultivated in Azerbaijan [6], among which such as tomato, potato, cucumber, cabbage, melon, pepper, pumpkin, beans, watermelon, eggplant, carrots, various greens, cereals, etc. prevail. It should be noted that among the cultivated plants there are many species that have medicinal value and have long been used in folk medicine. The research material was various crops that were traditionally cultivated in Azerbaijan. The materials were collected in the territories of the Lankaran-Astara (mainly Masalli district) region and the Absheron peninsula. According to the research conducted in 2020-2024, more than 500 samples were collected and analyzed from various plants. Sampling and isolation of fungi into a pure culture were carried out according to the method used in mycology [5]. The identification of fungi was carried out according to the determinant (7), which was compiled according to the cultural, morphological and physiological characteristics of fungi.

As a result of studying the mycobiota of 37 species of herbaceous plants that are culturally cultivated in Azerbaijan, 105 species of fungi were identified, among which fungi, anamorphic fungi of the genera *Alternaria* (*A.alternata*, *A.brassicae*, *A.cherizanthi*, *A.radicina*, *A. solani*), *Ascochyta* (*A.anethicola*, *A.betae*, *A.brassicae*, *A.brassicae predominate-rapae*, *A.capsici*, *A.cucumeris*, *A.lycopersici*, *A.pisi*, *A.phaseolorum*, *A.sojikota*), *Aspergillus* (*A. flavus*, *A.fumigatus*, *A.niger*, *A.ochraceus*, *A.versicolor*), *Fuzarium* (*F. avenaceum*, *F.bulbigenium*, *F.gibbosum*, *F.moniliforme*, *F. oxysporum*, *F.sambucinum*, *F.semitectum*, *F.solani*, *F. tabacinum*), *Penicillium* (*P.chrysogenum*, *P.cuclopium*, *P.expansum*, *P.griseolum*, *P.hirsutum*, *P.jaczewski*, *P.martensii*, *P.notatum*, *P. olivaceum*, *P.puberulum*, *P.sartorii*), *Botrytis* (*B.cinerea*), *Trichoderma* (*T.harzianum*, *T.viride*, *T.konigi*), *Septoria* (*S.cucurbitacearum*, *S.lucopersici*, *S.flagellifera*, *S.glycines*, *S.sojina*, *S.woronichini*, *S.pisi*, *S.melongenae*), *Cladosporium* (*C.gossypii*, *C.transchelii*, *C.herbarum*) *Colletotrichum* (*C.atramentarium*, *C.trungatum*, *C.savulescui*, *C.krugerianum*, *C.higginsianum*, *C.orbiculare*, *C.tabacum*, *C.pisi*), *Verticellium* (*V. dahliae*, *V. lycopersici*, *V.nigrescens*, *V. pulverulentum*), etc. A similar pattern, i.e. the predominance of anamorphic fungi, was observed in the mycobiota of individual plants, among which the tomato mycobiota turned out to be the richest in species composition (38 species). Fennel was unfavorable for the habitat of fungi, since only 12 species of mycobiota were found on these plants during research.

The stability of cultivated plants is a factor influencing the dynamics of populations of phytopathogenic fungi, although the reaction of various plant species to the development of diseases is largely determined by specific conditions (agrometeorological, ecological, etc.) [3]. The largest number of micromycetes cause various diseases of the studied plants. A significant number of micromycetes were found on last year's dead organs (stems, leaves, roots)

of plants. Among them there are both saprotrophic micromycetes and pathogenic species. During the research, only 105 species of fungi were found, although according to our and literary data, it was found that about 70 species of them (fungi of the genera: *Alternaria*-4 species, *Ascochyta*-5 species, *Aspergillus*-2 species, *Ceratocystis*-1, *Colletotrichum*-7 species, *Botrytis*-1 species, *Fusarium*-7 species, *Monilia*-1 species, *Penicillium* - 2 species, *Phoma* 3-species, *Peronospora* - 3 species, *Phylosticta*-5 species, *Puccinia* - 3 species, *Sclerotinia*-2 species, *Septoria*-5 species, *Uromyces* 2-species, *Verticellium*- 4 species, etc.) are phytopathogenic and can cause various diseases (necrosis, fusarium, spotting, powdery mildew, false powdery mildew, rust, white rot, gray rot, wilting). But their epiphytosis was not observed during the studies. The study established the organotropic specialization of micromycetes, which consisted in the fact that 69 species are found in the phylloplane of herbaceous plants, the vast majority of which also belong to anamorphic fungi of the class *Hyphomycetes* (41) and *Coelomycetes* (28). 28 species of fungi were found on the stems, among which were pathogens of drying and wilting of plants, dry rot of the rhizome, mold formation and other dangerous diseases.

21 species of these fungi have been found on the generative organs of plants. It was found

that the development of some diseases, especially fusarium, is progressive and in the period from 2020 to 2024 the spread of fusarium increased 5.6 times, and powdery mildew - 2.8 times.

As a rule, when developing a biological method to combat diseases caused by fungi, it is of paramount importance to search for populations of microorganisms, including fungi that limit the development of phytopathogens. Such properties are characterized by fungi of the genus *Trichoderma*, which are cosmopolitan and found in all types of soil [1; 2]. However, in the course of our research, only 3 species of this genus were found, which, in terms of frequency of occurrence, belong to random species, which also raises concerns about the need to take preventive measures to improve the phytosanitary condition of the soil, where plants of various, mainly food purposes, are culturally cultivated.

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